

Green Synthesis Of Cu/Cu₂O/CuO Nanostructures Using *Clausena Heptaphylla* (Roxb. Ex Dc.) Wight & Arn. For Biomedical Applications

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ABSTRACT

Green synthesis of nanoparticles has emerged as an eco-friendly and cost-effective alternative to conventional methods and also receives much attention due to their outstanding qualities. In the present study, copper-based nanostructures (Cu/Cu₂O/CuO) were synthesised using *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf extract, which acts as a capping and reducing agent. The as-prepared samples were characterized using UV-Visible Spectroscopy, X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analyses. Strong absorption was seen for the characteristic band of the green synthesized copper-based nanostructures, as indicated by the UV-visible spectra's peaks at 253 and 395 nm. From FTIR spectral analysis, a prominent and broad peak was identified at 475.27 and 1007.80 cm⁻¹, due to the functional groups of the bioactive compounds. The XRD analysis revealed the establishment of a crystalline nature with dominant cubic Cu₂O and monoclinic CuO phases. The SEM images indicated agglomerated cubic and polyhedral morphologies with nanoscale features. The antibacterial activity was assessed against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as the fungus *Candida albicans*, using the disc diffusion method, which showed a remarkable outcome. The nanostructures exhibited significant antimicrobial activity with a notable zone of inhibition against *Bacillus cereus* and *Enterobacter faecalis*. Antioxidant assay using DPPH demonstrated dose-dependent free radical scavenging with maximum inhibition of 77.7%. The results indicate that *Clausena heptaphylla* extract can be readily employed as a capping, stabilizing, and reducing agent for the efficient green synthesis of copper-based nanostructures for antimicrobial compounds. Thus, it is thought that the production of nanoparticles employing a low-cost and eco-friendly green approach enhanced the antibacterial activity and other prospective uses in the field of biomedical.

Keywords: Green synthesis, eco-friendly, nanoparticles, bioactive compounds, antimicrobial, biomedical.

INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology involves the fabrication of nanoparticles at a tiny scale, specifically between 1 and 100 nanometers, employing both physical and chemical methods, as well as biological procedures.^[1] Green synthesis helps the environment and eliminates the need for costly, harmful, or hazardous chemicals. Conventional physical and chemical processes use stabilizing chemicals to prevent the produced nanoparticles from clumping together and reducing agents to reduce metal ions, both of which can be harmful to cells and the environment. The green

synthesis method employs agents to create biocompatible nanoparticles, and the ability of the plant finally determines the stability and energy efficiency of these nanoparticles^[2,3]. Green fabrication of nanoparticles has gained attention because of its eco-friendliness and biocompatibility for utilization in multiple applications^[4]. Metal oxide nanoparticles (MONPs) possess outstanding qualities and possible applications, including Cu NPs^[5], Ce₂O₃ NPs^[6], Ag NPs, and ZnO NPs^[7], etc., and are already synthesized by green synthesis processes. Studies also revealed that many metallic nanoparticles have diverse biological and biochemical functions;

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however, copper nanoparticles (Cu NPs) have received significant attention recently. Because of their high surface-to-volume ratio and high degree of reactivity, copper-based nanoparticles are also potent, stable, and effective antibiotic, antifungal, and antimicrobial agents [5]. The synthesis of neuropeptides, control of cell signaling pathways, antioxidant defense, and cofactoring of numerous enzymes involved in immune cell function are just a few of the numerous functions copper plays in human health [7, 8]. Copper has a critical role in enzymatic functions, antioxidant defenses, and the elimination of pathogens in living organisms [8]. Although copper-based nanoparticles have important physicochemical, biocidal, and therapeutic uses, their toxicity to human cells and vital organs can also cause adverse effects. Before employing these NPs in medicine, it is crucial to assess this factor thoroughly [9]. As antibiotic-resistant microbes proliferate, new antimicrobial agents and materials must be developed. Metallic copper nanoparticles may therefore prove to be a beneficial antibacterial agent in the future.

The plant-mediated approach uses different parts of plants, such as roots, stems, fruits, seeds, and leaves, and is the least expensive and most environmentally beneficial method for synthesizing nanoparticles [2]. The synthesis of NPs, using plant extracts, shortens the time required for the synthesis process and improves large-scale production. Previous reports have been made regarding the green synthesis of metal oxide nanoparticles using plant extract from various sources, such as *Eclipta prostrata* [9], *Citrus limon* [10], *Curcuma longa* [11], *Gloriosa superba* [12], *Tinospora cordifolia* [13], *Cinnamomum camphora* [14], *Emblica officinalis* [15], *Cymbopogon citratus* [16], and *Euphorbia tirucalli* [17]. Herein, the current work focuses on the green synthesis of CuO NPs using *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf extract and the evaluation of its antimicrobial activity against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria strains, namely *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Enterobacter faecalis*, and *Candida albicans*, the fungal pathogen, by using the disc diffusion method.

Clausena heptaphylla (Roxb. Ex DC.) Wight & Arn. (Family – Rutaceae), a small tree and a significant medicinal herb have leaves that have a powerful scent

because they contain anethole, an essential oil that is valuable in the cosmetic, medicinal, and perfumery industries. In addition to its vermifuge, insecticidal, diuretic, and astringent qualities, the plant has been used in various traditional treatments to cure headaches, malaria, and muscle soreness [20, 21, 22]. In the present study, Cu/CuO nanoparticles were synthesized using *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf extract, in an eco-friendly manner; their physicochemical characterization techniques were done, and antimicrobial and antioxidant properties were compared with the standard. Therefore, to the best of our knowledge, no literature has yet been reported on the green synthesis of Cu/CuO using *C. heptaphylla* leaf extract as a capping or reducing agent to assess antimicrobial activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Preparation of Leaf Extract of *Clausena heptaphylla*

The fresh healthy leaves of *Clausena heptaphylla*, about 200g, were collected from Nelliyamphathy of Palakkad district during December 2024. The collected samples were thoroughly washed in running tap water, followed by distilled water to remove impurities, and then dried in open air to remove the moisture content. Then the sample was powdered using a mixer grinder for further phytochemical analysis. Plant extract was prepared by mixing 25g of the powdered sample in 250 mL of distilled water. The mixture was kept for 1 hour in a water bath at 70°C and stirred continuously. The extract was cooled at room temperature, filtered, centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes, and stored at 4°C for further analysis. Figure. 2.

Figure 1: *Clausena heptaphylla* Habit

Phytochemical screening of *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf

The *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf powder were completely submerged in an 80 % methanol solution. The mixture was allowed to macerate for 96 hours at room temperature, with intermittent shaking to enhance the extraction. After the maceration period, the mixture was passed through filter paper using a funnel to separate the solid residues from the liquid

extract. The collected filtrate was then concentrated by evaporation in a water bath at 45 °C. The phytochemical components found in the leaves of *Clausena heptaphylla*, such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, phenols, and terpenoids, were assessed using conventional testing techniques.^[24] To identify its phytochemical profile, a range of standardized methodologies was employed to detect specific bioactive constituents.^[25]

Green synthesis of copper-based nanostructures

Copper-based nanostructures were synthesized using a green method ^[4]. Accordingly, the aqueous leaf extract (10 ml) was added to 90 ml of 10mM of copper sulphate pentahydrate (1:9) in an Erlenmeyer flask to synthesize Nanostructures. The mixture was placed in a magnetic stirrer and maintained for 2 hours, with the pH constantly kept at an alkaline level by adding 1N NaOH. The mixture was kept until a light brown coloured mass was formed. The residue was separated by centrifugation at 10000 rpm for 15 minutes and then washed with distilled water. The pellets were dried in a hot air oven for 15 hours at 100 °C. Thermal decomposition was used to eliminate the impurities from green-synthesized Copper Nanostructures after calcinating at 300 °C for 3 hours ^[26]. The general schematic representation for green synthesis of CuNS was shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Graphical abstract of green synthesis of CuNS using *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf extract.

Characterization of copper-based nanostructures

A UV-Visible spectrophotometer was used to record the absorption spectrum of Copper Nanostructures to determine their respective absorption edges and maximum wavelength within the 200–800 nm. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to detect different functional groups that played their role as reducing, capping, and stabilizing agents during the biological synthesis of Copper Nanostructures and their spectral properties. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is normally utilized to determine the size, form, and shape of the biologically synthesized Copper Nanostructures. [27] The X-ray diffraction patterns were collected using a Bruker D8 diffractometer, and diffraction angles were measured at a range of 20 ° to 80 °. The particle size was calculated using the Scherrer formula as shown in the equation below.

$$D = k\lambda / B \cos \theta$$

Where D is the average particle size, radiation (0.15406 nm), K is the Scherrer constant, λ is the wavelength of the X-ray beam used, β is the Full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the peak and θ is the Bragg angle. [28]

Antimicrobial Activity

The antimicrobial activity of *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf extract and Copper based Nano structures (CuNS) were evaluated using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method, strictly adhering to the guidelines of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI,2021). Antimicrobial activity was evaluated against selected 5 strains of human pathogenic bacteria in the Mueller-Hinton Agar (MHA) medium and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) medium. Gram-positive strains like *Bacillus cereus* (MTCC 430), *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 96), *Enterobacter faecalis* (MTCC 439), Gram-negative strains like *Salmonella typhi* (MTCC 98), and *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 452), and the Fungal strain *Candida albicans* (MTCC 183), were procured from the Institute of Microbial Technology (IMTECH) in Chandigarh, India.

The selected strains were sub cultured on nutrient agar and NB broths to ensure experimental consistency.

(After Subculture, isolates were preserved at 4°C as stab culture for the long term.) Notably, all experiments were conducted using freshly grown cultures, minimizing variability and ensuring the reliability of the results. This meticulous approach to strain selection and culture maintenance laid the foundation for robust and meaningful research outcomes. The agar plates were prepared as per the manufacturer's instructions and checked for sterility by incubating them overnight at 37°C. The agar plates were then overlaid with the bacterial isolates' inoculum, showing the turbidity equivalent to that of a 0.5 McFarland standard, and the sterile antibiotic discs were placed on the plates. The discs were kept in the extracts for 12 hr before being placed on the agar plates. The zones of growth inhibition around the disc were measured after 24 hrs of incubation at 37°C for bacteria and fungi. [29]

The sensitivities of microbial species to the leaf extracts were determined by measuring the sizes of inhibitory zones (including the diameter of the disc) on the agar surface around the disc, and values less than 8 mm were considered as not active against microorganisms. The zones of inhibition, which were indications of anti-bacterial activity, were measured in millimeters using a transparent ruler, and the results were compared to the controls.

Antioxidant Activity

DPPH free radical scavenging activity [30] by Copper Nanostructures was evaluated using Ascorbic acid as a standard. [31]. 1 mL of 0.1 M DPPH was prepared in methanol and mixed with 1 mL of copper oxide nanoparticles of different Concentrations (0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, and 2.5mg/ml). Standard Ascorbic acid was used in the same concentration as the nanoparticles, and both were dark incubated for 30 minutes. The mixture of DPPH solution and each sample was vortexed for 30 seconds and then kept in the dark at room temperature for 30 minutes. During this incubation period, the antioxidant compounds in the extract and CuNS reacted with the DPPH radicals, causing a decolorization of the purple DPPH solution to a yellow colour. The degree of decolorization indicated the scavenging effectiveness of the extract and CuNS in neutralizing the DPPH free radicals. To measure the extent of decolourization, the absorbance of the

reaction mixtures was recorded at 517 nm using a UV-Visible Spectrophotometer. Lower absorbance values indicated higher free radical scavenging activity, suggesting a stronger antioxidant effect. The DPPH per cent of inhibition, which reflects the antioxidant activity of the extract and CuNS, was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Scavenging Activity (\%)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of Control} - \text{Absorbance of Sample}}{\text{Absorbance of Control}} * 100$$

Data analysis

All tests were done in triplicate, and the mean and standard deviations (SD) were determined using Microsoft Excel (2019 version). The results were expressed as mean \pm SD.

RESULTS:

The study showed that *C. heptaphylla* leaf extract, along with its phytochemical components are

responsible for the reduction of metallic ions and stabilization of the nanoparticles [31]. Furthermore, the green synthesis of CuNSs using *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf extract and its bioactive constituents imparts significant antifungal, antioxidant, and bactericidal activities against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens^[32].

Phytochemical Study

Phytochemicals present in the leaf extract were initially assessed using various chemical tests. The leaf extract does not contain starch, carbohydrates, or quinones, but possesses positive tests for Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Tannins, Saponins, Phenols, and Terpenoids as shown in TABLE 1. These classes of bioactive constituents are believed to act as reducing and stabilizing agents during the synthesis of nanomaterials.^[33] Studies suggest that phytochemicals such as tannins and flavonoids exhibit antibacterial properties and play a significant role in scavenging free radicals.

Table 1. Phytochemical analysis of *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf extract.

Phytochemicals	Remarks
Starch	-
Carbohydrates	-
Quinones	-
Alkaloids	+
Flavonoids	+
Tannins	+
Saponins	+
Phenols	+
Terpenoids	+

Where the symbol “+” indicates the presence of phytochemicals, and the symbol “-” denotes their absence.

Characterisation of copper-based nanostructures

The UV-Vis spectrum of the green-synthesised nanoparticles exhibited a distinct absorption peak at approximately 253 nm and 395 nm, indicative of the formation of copper oxide species, particularly Cu₂O (Fig. 3). This absorption band confirms the successful reduction of Cu²⁺ ions to copper oxide nanoparticles, facilitated by the phytochemicals present in the *Clausena* leaf extract. The observed band-edge

absorption in this region is characteristic of Cu₂O and further corroborates the presence of Cu₂O nanoparticles exhibiting quantum-size effects. Usually, copper nanoparticles exhibit absorption in the 280-360 nm range, which overlaps with the absorption of Cu, Cu₂O, and CuONPs. The FTIR spectrum displayed a characteristic band at 475.27 and 1007.80 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 4), which is attributed to the C-O stretching vibrations of alcohols, phenols, and carbohydrate groups present in the plant extract. This

finding confirms their role as reducing and capping agents. Additionally, a strong absorption band at 475.27 cm^{-1} corresponds to the Cu–O lattice vibration, indicating the formation of metal–oxygen bonds.

The XRD analysis confirmed the purity and crystallinity of the green-synthesized copper oxide nanoparticles (Fig. 5). The presence of phytochemical-related functional groups alongside the metal–oxygen bonds reinforces the effectiveness of the green synthesis process. The XRD pattern revealed that the nanoparticles using the aqueous

extract of *Clausena heptaphylla* show diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 29.57^\circ, 36.42^\circ, 42.31^\circ, 52.46^\circ, 61.38^\circ, 65.55^\circ, 69.54^\circ, 73.52^\circ, 77.38^\circ,$ and 84.94° . These peaks are indexed to the (110), (111), (200), (211), (220), (221), (310), (311), (222), and (321) planes of cubic cuprous oxide (Cu_2O). The XRD analysis showcased sharp diffraction peaks corresponding to the cubic Cu_2O phase, and the calculated lattice parameter ($a = 4.269\text{ \AA}$) aligned with standard cuprite values, confirming that Cu_2O is the dominant crystalline phase. It revealed that the synthesized Cu and Cu_2O have a cubic structure, and CuO has a monoclinic structure.

Figure 3 : V Visible Spectrum of Cu/CuONPs

Figure 4 : FTIR Spectrum of Cu/CuONPs

Figure 5: XRD Spectrum of Cu/CuONPs

SEM images taken at various magnifications (500 x to 10,000 x) illustrated the hierarchical micro-nano morphology of the synthesized nanoparticles (Fig. 6). SEM analysis disclosed that the Cu/Cu Oxides NPs have a cubic or monoclinic shape with an agglomerate nature [32]. At lower magnifications, the material was observed as dense agglomerates, which is typical for green-synthesized metal oxides due to aggregation mediated by biomolecules. At higher magnifications, well-defined cubic and polyhedral particles

characteristic of Cu/Cu Oxides nano phases became visible. The crystalline blocks measured between 0.5 and 1.5 μm , while numerous ultrafine spherical nanoparticles (approximately 20 to 80 nm) were distributed across their surfaces, indicating secondary nucleation. These morphological features suggest a nucleation-growth-aggregation mechanism, whereby phytochemicals first reduce Cu^{2+} ions, followed by the aggregation and fusion of these ions into larger crystalline units.

Figure 6: SEM image of Cu/CuONPs

The combined characterization conclusively demonstrates the successful green synthesis of crystalline Copper based nanostructures (CuNs). The plant extract not only reduced the copper ions but also supplied functional biomolecules that stabilized the nanoparticles and influenced their cubic morphology. The formation of both nanosized grains and microcubic aggregates highlights a natural, eco-friendly synthesis mechanism suitable for catalytic, antimicrobial, and environmental applications.

Antimicrobial Activity

The carbazole alkaloid, clausenal, is responsible for its antimicrobial activity of *Clausena heptaphylla*.^[33] This study aims to analyze whether CuNS synthesized from *Clausena heptaphylla* possess the antimicrobial activity comparable to that of a plant extract or not. The result disclosed that CuNS have higher antimicrobial activity compared to the plant extract. All experiments were carried out in triplicate, and the results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by comparison with the control, and values of $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

The antimicrobial activity of CuNS and *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf extract was evaluated using the disc

diffusion method, and the results demonstrated a concentration-dependent increase in activity. At a 5 mg/mL concentration, Cu nanostructures showed significant inhibition against all tested microbial strains when compared to the control and plant extract. The highest zone of inhibition was observed against *Bacillus cereus* (25 ± 0.30 mm) and *Enterobacter faecalis* (25 ± 0.32 mm), followed by *Escherichia coli* (20 ± 0.20 mm) and *Salmonella typhi* (18 ± 0.15 mm). The lowest activity was recorded against *Staphylococcus aureus* (7 ± 0.22 mm). The antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* also showed a considerable inhibition zone of 24 ± 0.18 mm at 5 mg/mL. (Table 2).

Statistical analysis revealed that the antimicrobial activity of Cu nanostructures at 5 mg/mL was highly significant ($p < 0.01$) compared to the plant extract and lower concentration (1 mg/mL), which showed no significant activity ($p > 0.05$). The methanolic leaf extract exhibited only moderate inhibition (7–10 mm), which was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than that of the nanoparticles (Figure 7). These results indicate that the synthesized Cu nanostructures possess enhanced antimicrobial efficiency, and the observed differences between concentrations confirm a statistically significant dose-dependent effect.

Table 2: Zone of inhibition of bacteria by disc diffusion assay

Organisms	Diameter of the zone of inhibition of				Significance (p-value) CuNs vs extract
	Control (mm)	1mg/ml (mm)	5mg/ml (mm)	Methanol extract (mm)	
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	24 ± 0.10	-	20 ± 0.20	10 ± 0.42	$P < 0.01$
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	27 ± 0.15	-	25 ± 0.30	10 ± 0.34	$P < 0.01$
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	27 ± 0.26	-	07 ± 0.22	08 ± 0.15	$P < 0.05$
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	24 ± 0.18	-	18 ± 0.15	07 ± 0.20	$P < 0.01$
<i>Enterobacter faecalis</i>	27 ± 0.42	-	25 ± 0.32	09 ± 0.15	$P < 0.01$
<i>Candida albicans</i>	29 ± 0.33	16 ± 0.25	24 ± 0.18	07 ± 0.10	$P < 0.01$

“ - ” indicates no significant activity. Values are mean \pm (n=3), $P < 0.05$ = significant, $P < 0.01$ highly significant

Figure 7: Antimicrobial activity of *Clausena heptaphylla*

In Vitro Antioxidant Assay

Antioxidant activity assessed by DPPH radical scavenging assay also showed a clear concentration-dependent increase in activity. With the increase in the concentration of nanoparticles, the antioxidant capacity also increased (Fig. 8). The percentage inhibition ranged from 69% to 77.7% for Cu nanostructures across concentrations of 0.5 to 2.5 mg/mL, while the standard ascorbic acid exhibited higher activity, ranging up to 98.91%. At the highest concentration (2.5 mg/mL), Cu nanostructures showed $77.7 \pm 0.45\%$ inhibition, which was statistically significant compared to lower concentrations ($p < 0.01$). The increase in antioxidant

activity with concentration was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming a dose-dependent trend. However, when compared with the standard ascorbic acid, the antioxidant activity of Cu nanostructures was significantly lower ($p < 0.01$), indicating that although the nanoparticles possess good radical scavenging ability, they are less potent than the standard. It is based on the capacity of Cu/Cu Oxides nanoparticles to donate free radicals and thereby prevent the oxidation of the cells [34]. Statistical evaluation using one-way ANOVA revealed that the antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of Cu nanostructures were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming a dose-dependent effect. (Table 3)

Table 3: Statistical analysis by one-way ANOVA

Concentrations (mg/ml)	CuNs (% inhibition)	Ascorbic acid (% inhibition)	Significance (p-value)
0.5	69.0 ± 0.35	85.2 ± 0.40	$P < 0.05$
1.0	71.5 ± 0.38	90.3 ± 0.32	$P < 0.05$
1.5	73.8 ± 0.42	94.1 ± 0.28	$P < 0.01$
2.0	75.6 ± 0.40	96.7 ± 0.30	$P < 0.01$
2.5	77.7 ± 0.45	98.9 ± 0.25	$P < 0.01$

Values expressed as mean \pm SD (n=3)

Figure 8: DPPH radical scavenging activity of CuNS

DISCUSSION:

The present study demonstrates the successful green synthesis of Cu/Cu₂O/CuO nanostructures using *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf extract, confirming the efficiency of plant-mediated synthesis routes. Green synthesis has gained significant attention in recent years due to its eco-friendly nature, cost-effectiveness, and avoidance of toxic chemicals typically used in conventional nanoparticle synthesis [35]. Phytochemicals such as flavonoids, phenols, and terpenoids present in the plant extract play crucial roles as reducing, capping, and stabilizing agents, thereby facilitating nanoparticle formation and stability.

The UV–Visible spectral peaks observed in this study are consistent with previously reported absorption bands for copper oxide nanoparticles, confirming successful nanoparticle formation. Similar studies using plant extracts have reported comparable absorption ranges and structural characteristics, indicating the reproducibility of green synthesis methods [36]. FTIR analysis further confirmed the involvement of functional groups, such as alcohols and phenols, in the reduction and stabilization processes, consistent with earlier findings indicating that biomolecules actively participated in nanoparticle synthesis. XRD analysis revealed the crystalline nature of the synthesized nanostructures, with dominant Cu₂O and CuO phases. The coexistence of

Cu, Cu₂O, and CuO phases suggests partial oxidation during synthesis, which is commonly observed in green synthesis due to varying redox conditions. Similar phase compositions and crystalline structures have been reported in recent studies on plant-mediated copper nanoparticles [37]. SEM analysis indicated agglomerated cubic and polyhedral morphologies, which may be attributed to biomolecule-induced aggregation during nanoparticle formation.

Studies have shown that CuO nanoparticles exhibit significant activity even against multidrug-resistant bacterial strains, primarily through oxidative stress mechanisms [38]. The enhanced antimicrobial activity at higher concentrations in this study supports the dose-dependent nature of nanoparticle toxicity reported in the literature. The antimicrobial mechanism is mainly attributed to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which induce oxidative damage to microbial cell membranes, proteins, and DNA. Additionally, the release of Cu⁺ and Cu²⁺ ions disrupts cellular integrity and interferes with enzymatic functions, leading to cell death. The high surface area of nanoparticles further enhances their interaction with microbial cells, increasing their effectiveness. Similar mechanisms have been widely reported in recent nanomaterial studies [39]. Recent studies have also reported that green-synthesized CuO nanoparticles exhibit dose-dependent antioxidant activity, supporting the findings of the present work

[39]. Furthermore, recent advancements in nanotechnology, such as Copper -based nanomaterials, have been explored for antimicrobial coatings, drug delivery systems, and treatment of infectious diseases, including *Helicobacter pylori* infections [40]. Additionally, the development of Copper-based nanocomposites has shown promising antibacterial, antifungal, and anticancer properties, highlighting their potential for advanced biomedical applications [41].

CONCLUSION:

This study is limited to the green synthesis, characterization, and evaluation of the antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of CuNS synthesized from the *Clausena heptaphylla* leaf extract. The antimicrobial activity of CuNS is strong against selected Gram-positive, Gram-negative, and *Candida albicans* pathogens. Preliminary phytochemical profiling of *C. heptaphylla* revealed the presence of various bioactive compounds, which can act as potent capping and reducing agents. The findings highlight the eco-friendly utilization of plant extracts in nanoparticle fabrication, offering an alternative to conventional chemical and physical synthesis methods.

Despite these promising results, the potential toxicity of copper nanoparticles must be considered. Excessive ROS generation may lead to cytotoxic effects in human cells, and therefore, further in vitro and in vivo studies are required to evaluate their safety and biocompatibility. Future research should focus on optimizing nanoparticle size, concentration, and surface modification to ensure safe biomedical applications. Overall, the findings of this study are in strong agreement with recent literature and confirm that *Clausena heptaphylla* mediated synthesis of copper-based nanostructures is an effective, sustainable, and promising approach for developing antimicrobial and antioxidant agents. Further comprehensive investigations are required to evaluate the stability, safety, and broader biomedical applications of CuNS, which may contribute to their potential use as therapeutic agents in medicine.

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